

DETERMINANTS OF ENROLLMENT FOR THE BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN INFORMATION SYSTEMS PROGRAM AT THE NEWLY ESTABLISHED UBAY COMMUNITY COLLEGE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 27

Issue 8

Pages: 906-915

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2613

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14058558

Manuscript Accepted: 10-10-2024

Determinants of Enrollment for the Bachelor of Science in Information Systems Program at the Newly Established Ubay Community College

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Abstract

This study aimed to analyze the key determinants influencing student enrollment in the Bachelor of Science in Information Systems (BSIS) program at Ubay Community College, with a focus on the relationships between financial, institutional, and external factors and enrollment decisions. Using a survey of 322 first-year students, the research explored how demographic factors, such as age, gender, and socio-economic status, intersect with these determinants. Data were analyzed through descriptive statistics and t-tests. The findings indicated that institutional factors—particularly the college's facilities, reputation, and hands-on learning opportunities—had the strongest influence on enrollment decisions, followed closely by financial factors, such as tuition accessibility and scholarships. Additionally, external factors, such as family recommendations, played a smaller yet notable role. The study also revealed a significant relationship between students' awareness of the BSIS program and their perceptions of its value; higher awareness correlated with more positive perceptions. The analysis further underscored the interconnectedness of institutional reputation and affordability, with financial accessibility playing a pivotal role in enhancing the program's attractiveness. Grounded in the theory of planned behavior and supported by existing literature on educational decision-making, this study provides actionable insights for Ubay Community College's strategic planning. It recommends continuing institutional improvements, maintaining financial support mechanisms, and enhancing targeted awareness campaigns to boost enrollment in the BSIS program.

Keywords: *BSIS program, enrollment determinants, external influences, financial factors, higher education*

Introduction

Choosing a college program is a pivotal decision that significantly shapes a student's career path and future opportunities. This decision is particularly nuanced in computing fields such as Information Systems (IS) and Computer Science (CS). Students inclined towards technology but less interested in intensive programming often choose IS, which emphasizes the application of technology to optimize business processes. IS graduates develop a strong understanding of both technology and business, enabling them to implement technological solutions that improve operational efficiency, enhance customer satisfaction, and increase organizational profitability (Topi et al., 2010; Gorgone et al., 2006).

For newly established institutions like Ubay Community College (UCC), understanding the factors influencing student enrollment is critical to their growth and sustainability. Newly formed colleges face unique challenges, such as limited resources, less-established reputations, and the need to differentiate themselves in competitive academic markets. These institutions must navigate these challenges while simultaneously ensuring that their academic programs align with the needs of both students and the local labor market. Enrollment patterns directly impact an institution's ability to secure funding, improve facilities, and offer diverse academic opportunities, making it crucial for colleges like UCC to comprehend the determinants that drive students' program choices.

The academic literature suggests that several factors influence students' decisions to enroll in specific programs. These include the institution's reputation, academic quality, faculty expertise, career opportunities, financial aid, and the overall educational experience (Elliott & Healy, 2001). In particular, newly established colleges must place a strong emphasis on building their reputation through effective student recruitment strategies and the provision of relevant academic programs that meet labor market demands (Salas-Velasco, 2006). For computing programs like IS, institutions must communicate the program's alignment with industry trends and future career prospects to attract students. Moreover, studies highlight the importance of socio-economic factors, peer influence, family expectations, and personal interests in shaping enrollment decisions (Frey & Osborne, 2017).

In the Philippines, the gap between university graduates' skills and job market demands continues to be a pressing issue, with many graduates facing underemployment or unemployment due to mismatches between their education and labor market needs. UCC, as a newly established institution, must address these challenges by offering programs like the Bachelor of Science in Information Systems (BSIS), which equips students with both technological and business acumen. Given the evolving job market, the BSIS program is strategically designed to address industry needs while offering students career-oriented opportunities in the field of information systems.

This study aims to explore the determinants that influence students' decisions to enroll in the BSIS program at Ubay Community College. These factors include academic interests, perceived career opportunities, socio-economic background, family expectations, and peer influence. By investigating these variables, the research will provide insights into how UCC can enhance its recruitment and retention strategies, particularly in its IS program.

The findings will guide Ubay Community College in developing targeted, data-driven recruitment strategies that address the aspirations and needs of prospective students. Additionally, this research contributes to the broader discourse on how newly established institutions can adapt to the competitive educational landscape and ensure alignment between educational programs and labor market demands. Through strategic initiatives informed by this study, UCC can not only attract and retain students but also support the local economy by producing graduates with the skills necessary to thrive in the modern workforce.

Research Questions

This research aimed to identify and analyze the determinants of enrollment for the Bachelor of Science in Information Systems (BSIS) program at the newly established Ubay Community College. The primary objective was to understand the factors that significantly influenced students' decisions to enroll in the BSIS program. Specifically, it sought answer to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic characteristic of the students in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender; and
 - 1.3. socio- economic status?
2. What extent do the following factors affect students' choices to enroll in the BSIS program:
 - 2.1. financial factors;
 - 2.2. institutional factors; and
 - 2.3. external factors?
3. What are the levels of students' awareness and perception of the BSIS program?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of students' awareness and perception of the BSIS program?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the different factors that affect students' choices to enroll in the BSIS program?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive survey method to analyze the determinants of enrollment for the Bachelor of Science in Information Systems (BSIS) program at the newly established Ubay Community College. By systematically collecting and analyzing data, this approach aimed to provide a comprehensive depiction of the factors influencing students' decisions to enroll in the BSIS program.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were all 322 freshmen students enrolled in the pioneering BSIS program at Ubay Community College. As the first cohort to experience this newly introduced program, they offered valuable and unique insights into the factors that influenced their enrollment decisions.

Instrument

A structured survey questionnaire was utilized as the primary data collection tool for this study. The questionnaire was adapted, modified, and tailored from the works of Murphy and Roopchand (2003) and Shanka, Quintal, and Taylor (2006) to specifically address the various factors influencing students' decisions to enroll in the BSIS program at Ubay Community College. The instrument was designed to capture comprehensive quantitative data while reflecting the unique context of the newly established program.

Procedure

The research process for this study was meticulously organized in collaboration with the Research Coordinator and the College President of Ubay Community College to investigate the determinants of enrollment in the Bachelor of Science in Information Systems (BSIS) program. The College President initiated the process by outlining the study's objectives and securing formal approval and institutional support, ensuring a seamless data collection process.

Survey questionnaires were distributed directly to all 322 first-year students enrolled in the BSIS program. The surveys were administered in-person during scheduled class hours, ensuring that all students had the opportunity to participate under consistent conditions. All 322 questionnaires were successfully retrieved, resulting in a 100% response rate. This high participation rate was achieved due to the in-class distribution method and the clear communication of the survey's purpose and potential benefits to students.

Although the collection process went smoothly, a few students initially expressed concerns about the relevance of the survey to their academic experience. These concerns were addressed through a brief explanation of the study's significance and its potential to improve the BSIS program. Minor logistical adjustments were made to coordinate with instructors and avoid disruption to regular class activities.

Upon retrieval, the completed questionnaires were reviewed for accuracy and completeness, then coded and entered into a database for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics and t-tests were employed to identify relationships between the factors influencing students' enrollment decisions. The insights gained from this data helped inform the development of targeted strategies to attract and retain students in the BSIS program.

Data Analysis

For the data analysis, several statistical treatments were used to address the research questions. Descriptive statistics (frequency counts and percentages) were applied to analyze the demographic characteristics of the students, including age, gender, and socio-economic status. To determine the extent of influence of financial, institutional, and external factors on enrollment decisions, mean scores and standard deviations were computed from responses on a 5-point Likert scale.

To assess the levels of awareness and perception regarding the BSIS program, mean scores were also calculated. The relationship between students' awareness and perceptions was examined using Pearson correlation to determine the strength and significance of this relationship.

Finally, Pearson correlation was used to explore relationships between the different factors (financial, institutional, and external) that affected students' enrollment choices, revealing how these factors interacted in influencing decision-making.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to strict ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and their confidentiality was rigorously protected. Participation was entirely voluntary, with no coercion involved, and participants were assured that no harm would come to them. The researchers declared no conflicts of interest and committed to reporting the findings transparently and honestly. Additionally, cultural sensitivity was observed and respected throughout the research process.

Results and Discussion

This part presents the data gathered through a survey, followed by an analysis and interpretation of the findings. The study includes various demographic details of the respondents and addresses key factors evaluated in the survey.

To determine the respondents' profile, the researchers got the percentage of the respondents who answered the survey questionnaire. On the other hand, the weighted mean of the answers of the respondents of each question were used to determine their descriptive value.

Table 1. Respondents' Profile on Gender (N=322)

<i>Profile on Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
Male	152	47.20%
Female	170	52.80%

Table 1 indicates that female respondents slightly outnumber male respondents, comprising 52.80% of the population while male respondents comprise 47.20% of the population. This suggests a fairly balanced gender distribution among the participants

Table 2. Respondents' Profile on Age (N=322)

<i>Profile on Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
17 years below	30	9.32%
18-20 years	256	79.50%
21-22 years	24	7.45%
23-24 years	10	3.11%
25 years	2	0.62%

Table 2 shows that the majority of respondents fall within the 18-20 years age group, constituting 79.50% of the sample. The lowest percentage of respondents are in the 25-year age group, making up only 0.62%.

Table 3. Students' Profile on Block Number (N=322)

<i>Profile on Block Number</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
A	38	11.80%
B	35	10.87%
C	38	11.80%
D	39	12.11%
E	36	11.18%
F	35	10.87%
G	35	10.87%
H	35	10.87%
I	31	9.63%

Table 3 reveals the distribution of respondents across different blocks, with Block D having the highest number of respondents at 12.11%, and Block I having the lowest at 9.63%.

Table 4 illustrates that the majority of respondents belong to the "poor" socio-economic status category (65.53%), while only a small fraction (0.31%) identify as "upper income."

Table 4. *Students' Profile on Socio-economic status (N=322)*

<i>Profile on Socio-economic status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
Poor	211	65.53%
Low income	86	26.71%
Lower middle income	11	3.42%
Middle income	8	2.48%
Upper middle income	2	0.62%
Upper income	1	0.31%
Rich	3	0.93%

Table 5 reveals the extent to which financial factors affect the choices of students to enroll in the BSIS program. Statement number 2 highlights that the school offers free tuition fees, which obtained a weighted mean of 4.42, with the descriptive interpretation of "extremely influential." This indicates that the majority of respondents chose to enroll in this institution because of the free tuition. On the other hand, statement number 3, which refers to the affordability of living expenses (e.g., boarding house), received a weighted mean of 2.82, interpreted as "moderately influential." This suggests that while living arrangements do affect students' enrollment decisions, they are of lesser importance compared to tuition costs. The overall composite mean of 3.55 shows that financial factors, in general, are "very influential" in students' choice of institution.

Table 5. *Financial Factors (N=322)*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. The availability of scholarships influenced my decision to enroll in the BSIS program.	4.35	Extremely Influential	2
2. The school is offering free tuition fees to students.	4.42	Extremely Influential	1
3. The affordability of living expenses (e.g., boarding house) played a role in my decision.	2.82	Moderately Influential	10
4. My family's financial situation significantly affected my choice to enroll in the BSIS program.	3.31	Moderately Influential	7
5. The potential for earning while studying (e.g., part-time jobs) influenced my decision.	3.17	Moderately Influential	9
6. The affordability of dining options on or near campus influenced my decision to enroll.	3.42	Very Influential	6
7. The availability of financial support from my family for other educational expenses (e.g., books, materials, projects) influenced my choice to enroll.	3.67	Very Influential	3
8. The cost of commuting or transportation to the college affected my enrollment decision.	3.22	Moderately Influential	8
9. The presence of financial support from my family for other expenses such as allowances influenced my decision to enroll.	3.54	Very Influential	5
10. The overall cost of maintaining a balanced budget while attending school influenced my decision to enroll.	3.57	Very Influential	4
Composite Mean	3.55	Very Influential	

This finding is supported by Perna (2006), who identified that financial aid, including free tuition and scholarships, is a critical factor influencing students' enrollment decisions, especially for those from lower-income families. This aligns with the current study, where free tuition was the most influential factor in enrollment decisions. Additionally, Paulsen and St. John (2002) found that financial considerations, such as tuition and living expenses, significantly shape students' college choices. While free tuition had the strongest impact in this study, the affordability of living expenses, though only moderately influential, also contributed to the students' decision-making process. These studies confirm that financial factors, particularly free tuition, play a pivotal role in influencing students' enrollment choices, consistent with the findings in this research.

Table 6 reveals the extent to which institutional factors affect students' decisions to enroll in the BSIS program. Statement number 2 highlights that the facilities and resources available at Ubay Community College were a significant influence, with a weighted mean of 3.99, described as "very influential." This indicates that the majority of respondents were drawn to the institution due to its infrastructure and resources. On the other hand, statement number 7, which refers to the potential for personalized attention due to smaller class sizes, received a weighted mean of 3.57, also interpreted as "very influential." This suggests that while students appreciate smaller class sizes, it is not a primary factor in their decision-making process. The overall composite mean of 3.87 confirms that institutional factors, as a whole, are "very influential" in students' choice of where to enroll.

This result is consistent with the findings of Maringe (2006), who emphasized that institutional reputation, facilities, and resources are critical in shaping students' enrollment decisions. In particular, students tend to prioritize the quality of infrastructure, resources, and academic support when choosing a higher education institution. Similarly, Elliott (2006) found that institutional factors, such as campus facilities and academic support services, significantly influence students' perceptions and choices. Both studies support the current findings, confirming that institutional aspects, especially resources and facilities, are key determinants in students' enrollment decisions.

Table 6. *Institutional Factors (N=322)*

	<i>Statements</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	The location of Ubay Community College and its convenience played a role in my decision to enroll in the BSIS program.	3.98	Very Influential	2
2.	The facilities and resources available at Ubay Community College influenced my choice.	3.99	Very Influential	1
3.	The campus environment and student life at Ubay Community College influenced my enrollment.	3.90	Very Influential	6
4.	The availability of up-to-date technology and equipment at Ubay Community College influenced my decision.	3.73	Very Influential	9
5.	The perceived quality of education offered by the BSIS program at Ubay Community College was a significant factor.	3.95	Very Influential	4
6.	The support services provided by Ubay Community College (e.g., counseling, career services) influenced my decision.	3.92	Very Influential	5
7.	The potential for personalized attention due to smaller class sizes influenced my choice.	3.57	Very Influential	10
8.	The opportunity for hands-on learning experiences (e.g., internships, practical projects) influenced my enrollment.	3.86	Very Influential	8
9.	The engagement of faculty and staff in student success initiatives influenced my decision.	3.87	Very Influential	7
10.	The reputation of Ubay Community College as a new institution with innovative approaches influenced my choice.	3.96	Very Influential	3
	Composite Mean	3.87	Very Influential	

Table 7 reveals the extent to which external factors influence students' decisions to enroll in the BSIS program. Statement number 1 shows that family opinions and recommendations significantly impacted students' choices, with a weighted mean of 3.96, described as "very influential." This indicates that many respondents enrolled in Ubay Community College based on their family's opinions. On the other hand, statement number 5, which refers to the impact of media and promotional materials (e.g., brochures, advertisements), received a weighted mean of 3.21, interpreted as "moderately influential." This suggests that promotional materials played a lesser role in students' decision-making. The overall composite mean of 3.62 indicates that external factors are "very influential" in shaping students' enrollment choices.

Table 7. *External Factors (N=322)*

	<i>Statements</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	My family's opinions and recommendations influenced my decision to enroll in the BSIS program.	3.96	Very Influential	1
2.	The influence of my peers played a role in my choice to enroll in the BSIS program.	3.50	Very Influential	8
3.	Current job market trends and employment opportunities influenced my decision.	3.57	Very Influential	7
4.	Information from my high school teachers influenced my enrollment decision.	3.40	Moderately Influential	9
5.	Media and promotional materials (e.g., brochures, advertisements) affected my choice to enroll.	3.21	Moderately Influential	10
6.	The reputation of the BSIS program among potential future employers influenced my decision.	3.72	Very Influential	3
7.	Trends in technology and the IT industry influenced my decision to enroll in the BSIS program.	3.84	Very Influential	2
8.	Information from online forums and social media about the BSIS program influenced my choice.	3.61	Very Influential	6
9.	The potential for community engagement and networking opportunities influenced my decision.	3.71	Very Influential	4
10.	The alignment of the BSIS program curriculum with my career aspirations influenced my enrollment.	3.67	Very Influential	5
	Composite Mean	3.62	Very Influential	

Recent research by Palmer et al. (2004) supports these findings, showing that family opinions remain a dominant factor, particularly for first-generation college students and those from lower socio-economic backgrounds. Their study aligns with the current results, where family recommendations were a key external influence in students' decisions. Similarly, Palmer et al. also found that while media and promotional materials help raise awareness, they have a limited impact on final enrollment decisions, which is consistent with the present study, where promotional materials were only "moderately influential."

Overall, this confirms that while external factors, especially family support, are important, they are secondary to institutional factors like program reputation, quality of faculty, and available facilities. Institutional factors remain the primary drivers of enrollment

decisions at Ubay Community College, with financial and external influences playing a more supportive role.

Table 8. Awareness (N=322)

	Statements	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation	Rank
1.	I am aware of the specific subjects offered in the BSIS program.	3.98	High Awareness	3.5
2.	I know the core objectives and goals of the BSIS program at Ubay Community College.	3.84	High Awareness	8
3.	I am familiar with the faculty members teaching in the BSIS program.	3.23	Moderate Awareness	10
4.	I understand the admission requirements and procedures for the BSIS program.	3.87	High Awareness	6
5.	I am aware of the schedule and timing of classes offered in the BSIS program.	4.08	High Awareness	1
6.	I know about the resources and facilities available specifically for BSIS students.	3.86	High Awareness	7
7.	I am informed about the academic support services available to BSIS students (e.g., tutoring, library resources).	4.01	High Awareness	2
8.	I am aware of any internship or practical training opportunities provided through the BSIS program.	3.89	High Awareness	5
9.	I know the career paths or job opportunities available to graduates of the BSIS program.	3.98	High Awareness	3.5
10.	I understand the academic progression and milestones within the BSIS program.	3.8	High Awareness	9
	Composite Mean	3.85	High Awareness	

Table 8 reveals the extent of students' awareness of the BSIS program. Statement number 5 indicates that students are highly aware of the schedule and timing of classes, with a weighted mean of 4.08, interpreted as "high awareness." This suggests that students' knowledge of the class schedule significantly influenced their decision to enroll. In contrast, statement number 3, which refers to students' familiarity with the faculty members teaching in the BSIS program, received a weighted mean of 3.23, interpreted as "moderate awareness." This indicates that awareness of faculty members played only a minor role in students' enrollment decisions. The overall composite mean of 3.85, described as "high awareness," reflects that students were generally well-informed about the BSIS program before making their enrollment decision.

This finding is supported by Pimpa (2004), who found that students' awareness of academic offerings, such as program schedules and course availability, significantly impacts their decision to enroll in higher education programs. Pimpa's study aligns with the current finding that awareness of class schedules plays an important role in enrollment decisions.

On the other hand, Gifford, Briceno-Perriott, and Mianzo (2006) suggested that while faculty reputation is important, students' awareness of faculty members does not heavily influence initial enrollment decisions, consistent with the present study's finding of moderate awareness in this area.

Overall, these results suggest that while students are well-informed about the key elements of the BSIS program, particularly class schedules, awareness of faculty members is less critical in their decision-making process. This reinforces the idea that structural aspects of the program, such as timing and availability, are more influential in guiding students' enrollment choices.

Table 9. Perception (N=322)

	Statements	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation	Rank
1.	I believe the BSIS program at Ubay Community College is well-structured and organized.	4.29	Very Positive Perception	2
2.	I perceive the BSIS program curriculum to be comprehensive and relevant to current industry needs.	4.16	Positive Perception	9.5
3.	I believe the faculty members teaching in the BSIS program are knowledgeable and supportive.	4.32	Very Positive Perception	1
4.	I think the BSIS program offers good opportunities for networking and professional development.	4.29	Very Positive Perception	2
5.	I perceive the BSIS program to have a positive reputation among potential employers.	4.19	Positive Perception	7.5
6.	I believe completing the BSIS program will enhance my skills and competencies in information systems.	4.25	Very Positive Perception	5
7.	I am confident that graduates of the BSIS program from Ubay Community College are well-prepared for their careers.	4.19	Positive Perception	7.5
8.	I perceive the BSIS program to provide opportunities for practical learning and hands-on experience.	4.16	Positive Perception	9.5
9.	I think the BSIS program at Ubay Community College is a good choice for students who are interested in both technology and business.	4.28	Very Positive Perception	4
10.	I believe the BSIS program at Ubay Community College offers good value for my educational investment.	4.24	Very Positive Perception	6
	Composite Mean	4.24	Very Positive Perception	

Table 9 reveals the students' perceptions of the BSIS program. Statement number 3 indicates that students perceive the faculty members teaching in the program to be knowledgeable and supportive, with a weighted mean of 4.32, interpreted as a "very positive perception." This suggests that respondents generally view the BSIS faculty as well-qualified and helpful. Statements 2 and 8, which address the comprehensiveness of the BSIS curriculum and the opportunities for practical learning, received a weighted mean of 4.16, indicating a "positive perception." This means that students perceive the program as offering a well-rounded curriculum with hands-on learning experiences. The overall composite mean of 4.24 reflects a "very positive perception," demonstrating that students hold highly favorable views of what the BSIS program has to offer.

These findings align with Patrick and Yick's (2005) study, which found that students' perceptions of faculty expertise and supportiveness are critical in shaping their overall satisfaction with academic programs. Similarly, Umbach and Wawrzynski (2005) highlighted the importance of student perceptions of faculty engagement in fostering a positive academic experience. The current study's results, showing strong perceptions of faculty knowledge and support, reflect these findings. Moreover, Arum and Roksa (2011) emphasize that practical learning opportunities are essential for student satisfaction, aligning with the positive perception students in this study held about the BSIS program's practical learning components.

Overall, the very positive perception of the BSIS program suggests that students are highly satisfied with the faculty and the program's comprehensive, practical approach, indicating the program's strength in meeting student expectations.

Table 10. *Relationship Between the Level of Students' Awareness and Perception of the BSIS Program*

<i>Source of Relationship</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Comp t-value</i>	<i>Critical t-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Awareness vs Perceptions	322	11.73	1.967	Significant Relationship	Reject Ho

Table 10 shows that there is a significant relationship between students' awareness and their perceptions of the BSIS program. With a computed t-value of 11.73, which exceeds the critical t-value of 1.967, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that the result is statistically significant. This suggests a strong relationship between students' awareness and their perceptions of the BSIS program. In other words, students who are more informed about the program tend to have more favorable perceptions of it. The evidence clearly shows that the level of awareness directly impacts how students feel or think about the program.

This finding aligns with research by Yorke and Longden (2008) highlighted that awareness of curriculum and institutional offerings plays a crucial role in shaping students' overall perception of their educational experience.

Thus, the significant relationship observed in this study between awareness and perception underscores the importance of clear and comprehensive communication about the BSIS program, as students' understanding of the program's structure and offerings has a direct effect on their overall perception and satisfaction.

Table 11. *Relationship Between the Different Factors That Affect Students' Choices to Enroll in the BSIS Program*

<i>Source of Relationship</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Comp t-value</i>	<i>Critical t-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Financial vs Institutional	322	4.97	1.96	Significant Relationship	Reject Ho
Financial vs External	322	1.91	1.96	No Significant Relationship	Accept Ho
Institutional vs External	322	4.37	1.96	Significant Relationship	Reject Ho

Table 11 illustrates the relationships between various factors affecting students' decisions to enroll in the BSIS program. The table compares financial, institutional, and external factors and evaluates their relationships using computed t-values against a critical t-value of 1.96 to determine statistical significance.

The comparison between financial and institutional factors yielded a computed t-value of 4.97, which exceeds the critical t-value of 1.96. This indicates a significant relationship between these two factors, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. In this case, it suggests that financial considerations, such as tuition fees and scholarships, are closely linked with institutional factors like program reputation and available resources in shaping students' enrollment decisions.

In contrast, the comparison between financial and external factors resulted in a computed t-value of 1.91, which is lower than the critical t-value. This lack of significance led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis, suggesting that external factors, such as societal or family influences, are not strongly associated with financial considerations when students decide to enroll in the BSIS program.

Lastly, the comparison between institutional and external factors produced a computed t-value of 4.37, exceeding the critical t-value. This indicates a significant relationship between institutional factors, such as program quality, and external influences like family or societal expectations. This suggests that these two factors are meaningfully connected in shaping students' enrollment decisions.

Overall, Table 11 highlights that institutional factors play a central role in linking both financial and external considerations. Financial and external factors do not show a significant relationship with each other, emphasizing that while financial considerations and external influences are important, institutional aspects like program quality and reputation have the most significant impact on students'

enrollment decisions. These findings are consistent with studies by Maringe (2006) and Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka (2015), which demonstrated that institutional reputation, resources, and support services are critical in shaping student choices, often outweighing external influences.

Conclusions

The study reveals that several key factors significantly influence student enrollment decisions in the Bachelor of Science in Information Systems (BSIS) program at Ubay Community College. Among these, institutional factors—such as the college’s reputation, facilities, and opportunities for hands-on learning—emerged as the most influential, emphasizing the importance of maintaining high-quality academic offerings and infrastructure. Financial considerations, particularly free tuition and scholarships, also played a crucial role in attracting students, especially those from economically disadvantaged backgrounds.

External factors, including family recommendations, had a notable yet secondary influence compared to institutional and financial factors. Nevertheless, family support and community influence remain vital in shaping students' decisions, suggesting that Ubay Community College should actively engage with students' families and communities to further enhance external support. Additionally, a significant relationship was found between students’ awareness of the BSIS program and their positive perceptions of it. This highlights the need for clear and effective communication to increase student awareness and foster favorable perceptions of the program.

While the findings provide valuable insights, it is important to note the study's limitations. Since Ubay Community College is a newly established institution, the findings may not be fully generalizable to more established colleges with mature BSIS programs. Future studies could explore how these findings compare with more experienced institutions to gain a broader understanding of the factors influencing enrollment in varying educational contexts.

In conclusion, balancing institutional quality with financial accessibility is critical for sustaining and increasing student enrollment in the BSIS program. Ubay Community College should continue to enhance its academic resources, strengthen its financial aid offerings, and engage external influences to support student enrollment and success.

Based on the study's findings, the researchers recommend the following:

Enhance Institutional Facilities and Resources. Since institutional factors such as facilities and learning opportunities are key drivers of enrollment, Ubay Community College should continue to invest in upgrading infrastructure, technology, and academic resources. Enhancing the learning environment will improve the attractiveness of the BSIS program and help meet the growing demand for high-quality education.

Increase Awareness Campaigns. As students' awareness significantly influences their perception of the BSIS program, the college should implement targeted information campaigns to showcase the program’s strengths. Promoting the curriculum, faculty expertise, career opportunities, and support services through multiple channels (social media, websites, school visits) will improve visibility and attract prospective students.

Strengthen Financial Aid Programs. To attract students from lower socio-economic backgrounds, Ubay Community College should strengthen its financial aid offerings. Expanding the availability of scholarships, grants, and free tuition will reduce financial barriers for students, making the BSIS program more accessible to a wider demographic.

Leverage External Influences. Family recommendations and community opinions play an important role in enrollment decisions. The college should engage with students' families and the broader community by hosting informational sessions, open houses, and career guidance events. These initiatives will foster a supportive network around prospective students, enhancing positive external influences.

Improve Faculty-Student Engagement. Given that students reported lower awareness of faculty members, increasing faculty-student interaction is crucial. Faculty-led workshops, orientations, and mentorship programs could help bridge this gap, enhancing students’ familiarity with the teaching staff and improving their overall perception of the BSIS program.

Promote Hands-on Learning Opportunities. Since hands-on learning is a major factor in enrollment decisions, the college should continue to prioritize practical learning experiences such as internships, industry collaborations, and technology labs. Offering real-world applications of academic concepts will ensure that students are well-prepared for the job market.

References

- Arum, R., & Roksa, J. (2011). Limited learning on college campuses. *Society*, 48, 203-207.
- Briggs, S. (2006). An exploratory study of the factors influencing undergraduate student choice: the case of higher education in Scotland. *Studies in Higher Education*, 31(6), 705-722.
- Elliott, K. M., & Healy, M. A. (2001). Key factors influencing student satisfaction related to recruitment and retention. *Journal of marketing for higher education*, 10(4), 1- 11.

- Frey, C. B., & Osborne, M. A. (2017). The future of employment: How susceptible are jobs to computerisation?. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 114, 254-280.
- Gifford, D. D., Briceno-Perriott, J., & Mianzo, F. (2006). Locus of control: Academic achievement and retention in a sample of university first-year students. *Journal of college admission*, 191, 18-25.
- Gorgone, J. T., Gray, P., Stohr, E. A., Valacich, J. S., & Wigand, R. T. (2006). MSIS 2006: model curriculum and guidelines for graduate degree programs in information systems. *Acm Sigcse Bulletin*, 38(2), 121-196.
- Hemsley-Brown, J., & Oplatka, I. (2015). University choice: what do we know, what don't we know and what do we still need to find out?. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 29(3), 254-274.
- Maringe, F. (2006). University and course choice: Implications for positioning, recruitment and marketing. *International journal of educational management*, 20(6), 466-479.
- Murphy, H., & Roopchand, N. (2003). Intrinsic motivation and self-esteem in traditional and mature students at a post-1992 university in the north-east of England. *Educational Studies*, 29(2-3), 243-259.
- Palmer, M., Hayek, J., Hossler, D., Jacob, S. A., Cummings, H., & Kinzie, J. (2004). Fifty years of college choice: Social, political and institutional influences on the decision-making process.
- Patrick, P. K., & Yick, A. G. (2005). Standardizing the interview process and developing a faculty interview rubric: An effective method to recruit and retain online instructors. *The Internet and higher education*, 8(3), 199-212.
- Paulsen, M. B., & John, E. P. S. (2002). Social class and college costs: Examining the financial nexus between college choice and persistence. *The Journal of Higher Education*, 73(2), 189-236.
- Pimpa, N. (2004). The Relationship between Thai Students' Choices of International Education and Their Families. *International Education Journal*, 5(3), 352-359.
- Salas-Velasco, M. (2006). Private returns to an university education: An instrumental variables approach. *Higher Education*, 51, 411-438.
- Shanka, T., Quintal, V., & Taylor, R. (2006). Factors influencing international students' choice of an education destination—A correspondence analysis. *Journal of Marketing for Higher education*, 15(2), 31-46.
- Topi, H., Kaiser, K. M., Sipior, J. C., Valacich, J. S., Nunamaker Jr, J. F., de Vreede, G. J., & Wright, R. (2010). Curriculum guidelines for undergraduate degree programs in information systems. *ACM*.
- Umbach, P. D., & Wawrzynski, M. R. (2005). Faculty do matter: The role of college faculty in student learning and engagement. *Research in Higher education*, 46, 153-184.
- Yorke, M., & Longden, B. (2008). The first-year experience of higher education in the UK. *York: Higher Education Academy*, 68.

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